

POLITECNICO
MILANO 1863

UNIVERSITÀ
DI TORINO

EuroCD 2025

8th European Cyclodextrin Conference

Book of Abstracts

9th-12th September 2025

Politecnico di Milano

EuroCD 2025 - 8th European Cyclodextrin Conference
Politecnico di Milano, 9th-12th September 2025

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EuroCD 2025 - 8th European Cyclodextrin Conference

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**POLITECNICO
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EuroCD 2025

Politecnico di Milano, Italy

Detailed Day-by-day Schedule/Program

Tuesday 9th September

11:00 - 15:30	Registration
15:30 - 16:00	Opening Isabella Nova - <i>Deputy rector</i> Marinella Levi - <i>Head of Department</i>
16:00 - 16:40	PL1 Frank Biedermann
16:40 - 17:00	KN1 Gjylje Hoti
17:00 - 17:20	OP1 Marco Agnes
17:20 - 17:40	OP2 Kasper S. Hedergaard
17:40 - 18:00	OP3 Sébastien Rigaud
18:00 - 18:20	OP4 Maddalena Sguizzato
18:30 - 21:00	Welcome cocktail

Wednesday 10th September

8:30 - 9:00	Registration
9:00 - 9:40	PL2 Andreas Bernkop-Schnürch
9:40 - 10:00	OP5 Antonino Mazzaglia
10:00 - 10:20	OP6 Vincent Dumouilla
10:20 - 10:40	OP7 Noemi Bognanni
10:40 - 11:00	Coffee
11:00 - 11:20	KN2 Lucio Melone
11:20 - 11:40	OP8 Nicolas Tinet
11:40 - 12:00	OP9 Anita Kiss
12:00 - 12:20	OP10 Cristina Parisi
12:20 - 12:40	OP11 Mary McNamara
12:40 - 13:00	OP12 Daniel Ondo
13:00 - 14:10	Lunch
14:10 - 14:30	OP13 Jindřich Jindřich
14:30 - 14:50	OP14 Saverio Aliberti
14:50 - 15:10	OP15 Milena Sorrenti
15:10 - 15:30	OP16 Yareli Rojas-Aguirre
15:30 - 16:40	Poster session + Coffee
16:40 - 18:00	FP
18:30 - 21:00	Guided tour

Thursday 11th September

9:00 - 9:40	PL3 David H. Thompson
9:40 - 10:00	OP17 Francesca Laneri
10:00 - 10:20	OP18 François-Xavier Legrand
10:20 - 10:40	OP19 Ana-Maria Resmerita
10:40 - 11:00	Coffee
11:00 - 11:20	OP20 Damien Truffin, Julien Parcq
11:20 - 11:40	OP21 Carmen Alvarez-Lorenzo
11:40 - 12:00	OP22 Elisabetta Lacolla
12:00 - 12:20	OP23 Sylvain Laclef
12:20 - 12:40	OP24 Adrian Matencio
12:40 - 13:00	OP25 Balazs Kondoros
13:00 - 14:10	Lunch
14:10 - 14:30	KN3 Sophie Fourmentin
14:30 - 14:50	OP26 Giuseppe Nocito
14:50 - 15:10	OP27 Paolo Di Gianvincenzo
15:10 - 15:30	OP28 Yoshinori Takashima
15:30 - 15:50	OP29 Mariachiara Trapani
15:50 - 17:00	Poster session + Coffee
17:00 - 18:20	FP
20:30 - 23:00	Social dinner

Friday 12th September

9:00 - 9:40	PL4 Ruxandra Gref
9:40 - 10:00	OP30 Daniel I. Hädärugä
10:00 - 10:20	OP31 Antonella Vitiello
10:20 - 10:40	OP32 Siddanth Saxena
10:40 - 11:00	Coffee
11:00 - 11:20	KN4 Milo Malanga
11:20 - 11:40	OP33 Michal Řezanka
11:40 - 12:00	OP34 Askar Gatiatulin
12:00 - 12:20	OP35 Bettina Rávai
12:20 - 12:40	OP36 Angela Scala
12:40 - 13:15	1st T. Loftsson Award
13:15 - 13:30	Concluding remarks

PL: Plenary Lecture

OP: Oral Presentation

KN: Keynote Presentation

FP: Flash Presentation

Keynote Presentations

Greener Rings: Sustainable Strategies for Cyclodextrin Derivatives

Milo Malanga, Kristóf Felegyi, Daniel Bisericaru, Mihály Bálint

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Traditional syntheses of cyclodextrin (CD) derivatives often rely on harsh reagents and energy-intensive processes, raising environmental and efficiency concerns. Poor atom economy further compromises sustainability, while complex reactions and purification steps hinder scalability—highlighting the need for greener alternatives. Key derivatives such as 2-hydroxypropyl- β -CD (HPBCD), randomly methylated β -CD, and sulfobutylether- β -CD require highly reactive alkylating agents that are toxic, flammable, and volatile. CD intermediates like per-6-halogenated and per-6-silylated CDs are typically synthesized in organic solvents that are increasingly subject to regulatory restrictions. Cationic amphiphilic CDs—among the most promising CD-based excipients for nucleic acid delivery—require multi-step syntheses and chromatographic purification, which pose major barriers to industrial scalability. Likewise, water-soluble CD-based polymers derived from epichlorohydrin, citric acid, or nanosponge technologies rely on reactive crosslinkers and harsh conditions, leading to additional environmental and regulatory challenges. This work critically assesses production strategies for these CD derivatives, emphasizing recent advances in greener approaches aimed at process simplification, solvent and waste reduction, and enhanced industrial feasibility in line with green chemistry principles.

Figure 1. Overview of key parameters defining a green synthetic strategy.

Acknowledgements: HORIZON-MSCA-SE-01-01 2022 Bicyclos project #101130235.

Oral Presentations

CD-polymers as supramolecular, hydrophilic platforms for phototriggered multicomponent reactions in flow

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To meet the target set by the EU Green Deal and significantly decrease human impact on the planet by 2050, a strategy is to prioritize safe and sustainable-by-design (SSbD) materials for the development of less impacting catalytic processes in homogeneous aqueous environment.

Cyclodextrin-polymers (CDPs) crosslinked with epichlorohydrin are able to i) organize in nanoparticles of diameter 20-50 nm, ii) increase the solubility of parent CDs up to 100 times and iii) co-solubilize more guests simultaneously, thanks to the assorted hydrophobic cavities and pockets.[1] Recently they have been shown to allow the photooxygenation of aromatic substrates at millimolar concentrations in water.[2] We further capitalized on the use of customized CDPs to perform highly efficient, photocatalytic reactions in homogeneous aqueous phase, in flow,[3] selected thiol-ene photo-additions and photooxygenations upon supramolecular loading of reactants into CDPs labelled with Photo-Active Ingredients (PAIs). Following a computational screening, the target reactions were optimized to achieve higher efficiency and selectivity in a photoreactor in flow.

With our first results we endorse our forecast on CDPs as blockbuster SSbD matrix to perform homogeneous photocatalysis in greener conditions enabling unprecedented large scale chemical productions and boosting novel pharmacological and environmental applications.

Figure 1. General strategy applying designed PAI-CDPs to the photo-induced conversion of organic substrates in homogeneous aqueous environment.

Acknowledgements: HORIZON-MSCA-SE-01-01 **2022** Bicyclos project #101130235; Fondazione di partecipazione ECOSISTER (ART-ER) Next Generation EU, PNRR-MUR.

[1] M. Agnes *et al.*, *Macromol. Biosci.* (2022) 22, 2200090; M. Agnes *et al.*, *J. Mater Chem. B* (2024) 12, 7969-7976.

[2] M. Agnes *et al.*, *Chem. Eur. J.* (2023) e202300511.

[3] M. Agnes *et al.*, *Eur. J. Org. Chem.* (2024) 27, e202400861.

Evaluation of a Drug Delivery System based on Cyclodextrins

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Many chemotherapy drugs are successfully used today, with, however, some limitations which include negative side effects and individual patient sensitivities. These limitations can be mitigated by drug delivery systems that can target cancer cells and deliver the therapeutic dose to the required site of action. In this study, cyclodextrins are used for targeting folate receptors (FR) and delivering the drug methotrexate (MTX). FRs are over-expressed in cancer cells and uptake of folic acid is mediated with high affinity by FRs. Uptake of antifolates, such as MTX, is mediated with high affinity by the reduced folate carriers (RFCs) and MTX acts by inhibiting folate metabolism.

This study addresses gene (mRNA) and protein expression levels of FRs and RFCs in a range of cell lines and cell viability assays were used to assess the cytotoxicity of folate-modified cyclodextrin CDEnFA and the complex CDEnFA:MTX. Results demonstrate that the complex showed greater cytotoxicity than the free drug towards the high FR expressing KB and CaCo-2 cells, indicating that it has potential to target this receptor, enhancing drug specificity and efficiency.

Protein inhibition was used to understand uptake of MTX and fumonisins-B1 and sulfasalazine were used to inhibit FRs and RFCs, respectively. The results demonstrated a decreased cytotoxicity caused by the MTX after inhibition of RFCs, confirming its internalisation through this transporter. The results also demonstrated that the cytotoxicity caused by CDEnFA:MTX is decreased after inhibition of each receptor and significantly decreased after a co-treatment that inhibits both transporters. This indicates that the cytotoxic effect from the complex CDEnFA:MTX can be a result of drug uptake through two routes shown in Figure 1: (1) The CDEnFA:MTX binds to FR on the cell membrane and this receptor internalises the whole complex by endocytosis. (2) after CDEnFA:MTX binds to FR, MTX is released from the cyclodextrin cavity and internalised through the RFC. By using both of these routes, CDEnFA:MTX can amplify the cytotoxic effect of the drug MTX.

Figure 1: Folic acid targets the FR and (1) entire CDEnFA:MTX is internalised and MTX is released in endocytic vesicles (adapted from Endocyte, inc) and (2), CDEnFA remains extracellular and MTX is internalised through RFC.

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A little cyclodextrin here, a little cyclodextrin there

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Cyclodextrins (CDs) are everywhere. This presentation offers a review-based analysis of currently marketed CD-containing drug products, with a specific emphasis on APIs that are commercialized in more than one dosage form or administered *via* different routes. A key focus is placed on identifying and comparing those APIs that exist in multiple CD-based formulations, sometimes different types of CDs are employed depending on the formulation needs.

By reviewing data from scientific publications, review articles, and patent documents, we aim to uncover formulation strategies that use the versatility of CDs across various pharmaceutical platforms. The presentation discusses the choice of CD types in each dosage form, as well as how their physicochemical and regulatory properties influence product development. Trends in dosage forms, routes of administration, therapeutic indications, and the role of CDs in overcoming formulation challenges are also explored in detail.

The review highlights both well-established CD-based products and identifies potential gaps in the market, cases where promising CD-API combinations have been proposed in the literature or patents but are not yet commercially available. This analysis aims to inform and inspire formulation scientists and developers by showing the formulation flexibility of CDs and pointing toward new opportunities for innovation in drug delivery.

Acknowledgements: The author acknowledges funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement Bicyclos no. 101130235.

Flash Presentations

Synthesis of CD-derivatives for photoinduced therapeutic regimes bypassing hypoxia

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Hypoxia is a condition characterized by low concentrations of molecular oxygen in poorly vascularized tissues, which occurs, among other diseases, in solid tumours and microbial or fungal infections. In such hypoxic regions, the efficacy of both drug-based and photo-induced therapies is significantly reduced, thus restoring optimal oxygen levels is a primary goal to improve treatment outcomes. A promising strategy is to combine well-established drugs (i.e. chemotherapeutics, antimicrobial agents and photosensitizers) with aromatic endoperoxides, which act as oxygen releasing agents (ORAs). In this frame, we synthesized 9,10-disubstituted anthracenes able to reversibly bind and release oxygen upon thermolysis in physiologically compatible conditions, thereby restoring optimal oxygen levels in hypoxic environments.¹ Noticeably, the endoperoxide preparation was optimized under flow conditions in homogeneous aqueous environment.² We will present the first results on the synthesis of cyclodextrin-based derivatives functionalised with disubstituted anthracenes and photosensitizers, with the ultimate goal of developing an optimized platform capable of delivering simultaneously three different therapeutical agents for the treatment of cancer or microbial infections. To achieve the three-component synergistic therapeutic effect, we investigated various strategies involving both covalent conjugation and supramolecular loading onto a cyclodextrin-based platform, with emphasis both on its synthesis and therapeutic performance.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of a cyclodextrin-based platform able to carry contemporarily ORAs, photosensitizers and chemotherapeutical or antimicrobial drug.

Acknowledgements: This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement Bicyclos N°101130235.

- [1] M. Agnes, A. Santagata, D. Veclani, A. Venturini, M. Monari, P. Dambruoso, I. Manet, *Eur. J. Org. Chem.* (2024) 27, e202400861.
[2] M. Agnes, A. Mazza, E. Kalydi, S. Béni, M. Malanga, I. Manet, *Chem. Eur. J.* (2023) 29, e202300511.

Small Ring – Big impact

Tamas Sohajda

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How will cyclodextrins influence our future?

Cyclodextrins, once a niche topic of academic curiosity, have grown into versatile enablers of innovation across multiple sectors. While their pharmaceutical applications are well-documented, this presentation will highlight a series of case studies that trace the journey of cyclodextrin-based technologies from academic research to market success in non-pharmaceutical industries such as cosmetics, food, and environmental protection.

Each case study will explore the critical turning points—both scientific and strategic—that influenced the innovation path, including formulation challenges, regulatory considerations, scale-up limitations, and market positioning. The presentation will examine the broader industrial and economic contexts that shape the development of new technologies, with special attention to collaboration models, intellectual property strategies, and the role of industry-specific demands.

By analyzing real-world examples, the talk will provide insights into what makes a cyclodextrin-based innovation not only scientifically viable but also commercially sustainable. The goal is to foster discussion around how academic research can more effectively align with industrial needs to accelerate technology transfer and value creation.

Acknowledgements: The author acknowledges funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement Bicyclos no. 101130235.

Poster Session

Advancing UDP-003, a First-in-Class Therapeutic Targeting Oxidized Cholesterol to Reverse Atherosclerosis

Keivan Sadrerafi¹, Daniel M. Clemens¹, Amelia M. Anderson¹, Darren Dinh¹, Perna Bhargava¹, Fadzai Taramayi¹, Ana Silberg¹, Noah Rosenberg¹ and Matthew S. O'Connor¹

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Cardiovascular disease (CVD) remains the leading global cause of death, with current therapies unable to fully address its progression. Cyclarity Therapeutics has developed a novel class of cyclodextrin-based therapeutics designed to eliminate 7-ketocholesterol (7KC), a cytotoxic oxidized cholesterol implicated in foam cell formation and plaque development. UDP-003, a dimerized and selectively engineered cyclodextrin, binds and removes 7KC from biological systems with high specificity. In vitro studies show its capacity to prevent and reverse foam cell formation, and in vivo testing confirms selective clearance of 7KC. IND-enabling studies in both rodent and swine models demonstrate a favorable safety profile with no CYP, transporter, or ototoxicity-related liabilities. UDP-003 is excreted unchanged in urine and shows no systemic metabolic burden. The first-in-human trial is ongoing in Australia, in partnership with the Victoria Heart Institute. UDP-003 represents a new disease-modifying approach in the treatment of atherosclerotic disease.

Figure 1. Atherosclerosis, 7KC, and CDs.

- [1] A.M. Anderson, T. Kirtadze, M. Malanga, D. Dinh, C. Barnes, A. Campo, D.M. Clemens, R. Garcia-Fandiño, Á. Piñeiro, M.S. O'Connor, *Int. J. Pharm.* (2021) 606, 120522.
- [2] A. Anderson, A. Campo, E. Fulton, A. Corwin, W.G. Jerome, M.S. O'Connor, *Redox Biol.* (2020), 29, 101380.